

MA'NO KO'CHISHLARINING O'ZBEK TILIDAGI O'RNI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada tilimizda mavjud so'zlar ma'nolarining o'sishi, ma'no ko'chishi, ma'no kengayishi yo torayishi hodisalari ro'y berishi, borliqdagi narsa-hodisa, belgi-xususiyat, harakat-holat nomlari ma'lum bir asos-ga ko'ra boshqa narsa-hodisa, belgi-xususiyat, harakat-holatning nomi sifatida xizmat qilishi haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Metafora, sinekdoxa, metonimiya, vazifadoshlik, kinoya, ekspressivlik va ko'chma ma'no.

So'zlarda ma'no ko'chishi nima asosida ko'chishiga ko'ra metafora, sinekdoxa vazifadoshlik va kinoya kabi turlarga bo'linadi. Nutqda so'zlarning o'ziga xos ekspressivligini ta'minlash uchun ushbu ma'no ko'chishlaridan foydalaniladi. Metafora – nutqimizda eng keng tarqalgan ma'no ko'chish usuli hisoblanadi. Metafora (yunoncha – ko'chirish) bir predmet nomining boshqa predmetga o'xshashlik asosida ko'chirishdir. Tandirning og'zi birikmasida “og'iz” so'zining ma'nosi odam yoki hayvon og'ziga tashqi o'xshashlik asosida vujudga kelgan.

Demak, metaforada predmet, belgi, harakatlar o'xshashlik asosida boshqa predmet va harakatga ko'chadi. Masalan: qozonning qulog'i, varrakning dumi, kemaning tumshug'i, egarning qoshi, o'choqning og'zi, tog'ning etagi, qora niyat, sovuq xabar, shirin xotira, kumush qish, po'lat iroda, temir intizom va hokazo. Narsa va hodisalar o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik turli asosda bo'lishi mumkin: a) ikki predmet o'rtasidagi shakliy o'xshashlik: odamning qulog'i-qozonning qulog'i b) ikki predmetning qayerda joylashishi bo'yicha o'xshashlik: samolyotning dumi – itning dumi. Mavhum va aniq otlar shaklidagi ko'chma ma'noli birikmalar ham odatda, metaforani yuzaga keltiradi. Masalan: hayot ostonasi, visol uyi, ishq bog'i, hayo ko'chasi, takabburlik libosi bular adabiyotshunoslikda istiora deb nomlanadi. Metaforaga juda yaqin bir vosita „o'xshatishlar” bo'lib, ular yordamida shaxs, predmet bir-biriga o'xshatiladi, qiyoslanadi: -day, -dek, go'yo, yanglig', singari, xuddi, kabi o'xshatish vositalaridan ham foydalaniladi. Masalan: Ulug'bek misoli oftob. Nutq jarayonida metaforadan o'rinli foydalanish nutqimizni ta'sirchan jozibali qiladi. So'zlovchining badiiy-estetik qobiliyatini namoyon etadi.

Metonimiya yunoncha “qayta nomlash” degani. Narsa va hodisalar o’rtasida makon va zamondagi o’zaro aloqadorlik asosida birining nomi ikkinchisiga ko’chishi metonimiya deyiladi. Masalan: Fuzuliyning oldim qo’limga (Fuzuliyning asarlarini) shoir va uning asarlari o’rtasidagi bog’liqlik, samovarda osh yedik (choyxonada; choy ichiladigan joy bilan choy qaynatiladigan joy o’rtasidagi bog’liqlik). Zal kulib yubordi (Zaldagi odamlar). “Besh bolali yigitcha keldimi?” (kitobxon savolidan). Ichak-chavog’im qolmadi, endi kalla sotaman (qassobning gapi). Demak so’zlarning o’xshashlik emas, makon va zamondagi o’zaro bog’liqlik, aloqadorlik asosida ko’chma ma’no hosil qilish fikrimizni lo’nda, ifodali, ta’-sirchan bayon qilishning bir yo’li sanaladi.

Sinekdoxa yunoncha birgalikda anglash yoki nazarda tutmoq, qo’shib fahmlamoq so’zidan olingan bo’lib bo’lak orqali butunni yoki butun orqali qismni ang-latadi. Sinekdoxa metonimiyaning bir ko’rinishi bo’lib bunda ma’no butun va qism munosabatlari asosida ko’chadi. Shunga ko’ra sinekdoxa ikki xil bo’ladi: a) qism orqali butunni yoki b) butun orqali qismni ifodalash mumkin. Tirnoqqa zor bo’ldi (farzandga zor bo’ldi). Bitta shu tuyoq bilan besh bolani qanday boqaman (tuyoq deganda sigir, echki yoki boshqa bir hayvon tushuniladi). Ma’no ko’chishining bu turi ham nutqimizning ta’-sirchanligini oshirishda, ifodali va jozibali bo’lishida katta ahamiyatga ega.

Vazifadoshlik narsa va hodisalar o’rtasidagi vazifaviy bir xillik asosida birining nomi orqali ikkinchisining ifodalanishidir. Masalan: Ko’chalarni chiroqlar yop-yorug’ qilib turibdi. Chiroq piligini pasaytirdi. Yuqoridagi ikki gapda qo’llangan chiroq so’zi bir xil vazifa bajaruvchi ikkita bir-biriga o’xshamaydigan narsalarni ifodalaydi. Birinchi gapda elektr toki orqali yorituvchi lampochkani, ikkinchi gapda esa kerosinga pilik solish vositasi bilan yonuvchi asos va shisha qismdan iborat asbobni bildiradi. Bu asboblarning makon va zamonda aloqadorligi yo’q. Bu asboblarning shakliga ko’ra bir-biriga o’xshamaydi. Lekin vazifasi bir ular vazifadosh yani yoritish vazifasini bajaradi. Vazifadoshlik o’xshashlikka asoslanishi bilan metaforaga o’xshaydi. Farqi shundaki metaforada predmetning belgi, harakat o’xshashligi asos qilib olinadi. Bazen ma’no ko’chishida metafora va vazifadoshlik usullari birga qo’llanishi mumkin. Bu tilshunoslikda funksional metafora deb nomlanadi. Masalan: Odamning tishi-arraning tishi (bunda ham shakl, ham vazifa o’xshashligi mavjud). Vazifadoshlik asosida

vujudga kelgan soʻzlarni bilish ularning ilgari qanday shakldaligini bilishimiz, imkoniyatlari naqadar boy ekanligini his qilishimizga yordam beradi.

Kinoya arabcha bir narsa demoq boshqa narsa tushunmoq manosini bildiradi. Bunda soʻzlar oʻz maʼnosida emas, balki teskari aks maʼnoda tushuniladi. Kinoya usuli ogʻzaki nutqda maxsus intonatsiya ohang yordamida jozibali qilinadi, yozma nutqda esa qoʻshirnoqqa olish orqali ifoda etiladi. Masalan: Feruz nemis tilini “suv qilib ichgan”. Jasur urishganda bisotidagi bor “chiroyli” soʻzlarni ishlatadi.

Oʻzbek tilida maʼno koʻchishlari soʻzlashuv uslubi va badiiy uslublarda qoʻllaniladi. Badiiy adabiyot noyob tasvirlarni yaratishga va muallifning taqdimot uslubini boyitishga imkon beradigan yoʻllarning mavjudligi bilan boshqa uslublardan tubdan farq qiladi va bunda metonimiyadan keng foydalaniladi. Maʼno koʻchishining metonimiya turi tilning boy tarkibiy shakllari koʻrsatish, ekspressivligi va tasvirni berish uchun ishlatiladi. Metonimiya ritorika, poetika va leksikologiyada keng tarqalgan.

Metafora tasvir yaratish uchun soʻz yoki iborani majoziy maʼnoda qoʻllash. Maʼno koʻchishlari yordamida yozuvchi va shoirlar yorqin va rang-barang tasvirlar bilan boyitilgan oʻlmas asarlar yaratishadi. Soʻz yozuvchining vosita quroli hisoblanadi. Soʻz asarning barcha unsurlari: syujet, til, obraz, kompozitsiya, badiiylikni yuzaga chiqaruvchi asosiy moddiy vosita boʻlib, ijodkor isteʼdodi va tasvir uslubining koʻzgusi hamdir. Adabiy asardagi soʻz badiiy soʻzdir. Lekin har qanday soʻz ijodkor munosabatisiz badiiy boʻla olmaydi. Badiiy obraz ham soʻz orqali yaratiladi va bunda maʼno koʻchishlaridan mohirona foydalaniladi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo’lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o’zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o’zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo’lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og’ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo’llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE’S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

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¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov’s Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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